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New Students' Perceptions on the Implementation of Zoning-Based PPDB

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the perceptions of new students on the implementation of zoning-based PPDB (New Learner Admission Activities). The method in this research was mixed-method approach. Primary data was obtained through distributing questionnaires filled out by students. Samples were taken using purposive sampling technique in five cities, including Bandung, Surakarta, Surabaya, Pontianak and Serang. The data analysis technique used the Miles and Huberman model. The results show that the school which initially received the favourite label is still the favourite one because of the facilities and infrastructure and the implementation of the existing learning process in the school. The zoning system based on student perceptions does not reduce enthusiasm for learning. The zoning-based PPDB for junior high school and senior high school is more guaranteed for students who live close to the school to get the target school. The zoning system has been well implemented in four cities, including Surabaya, Bandung, Surakarta and Pontianak. In addition, the zoning system can save money.

Keywords: Students' Perception, Zoning-Based PPDB

Introduction

Education became a basic necessity for everyone in this Globalization Era. Education is a conscious and planned effort to realize learning process, so learners can actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble moral, as well as the necessary skills of themselves, society, nation and country (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 on The National Education System Article 1 Paragraph 1).

Education is a conscious effort for society development based on a certain rationale, such as philosophy view and socio-cultural background of the society (Siswoyo, 2013: 1). Therefore, it can be concluded that education is a conscious and planned effort based on certain thoughts to realize learning that is able to develop individual potential.

Education can be conducted formally, non-formally or informally in the society. Formal education is a structured and tiered educational system. Formal education includes primary, secondary and higher education (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System Article 1 Paragraph 11).

Education consists of components influencing each other including educational objectives, educators, learners, educational tools, educational methods, educational materials and environment (Hangestiningsih, 2015: 27). Besides, education can be constructed of educators, learners, educational objectives, educational tools and educational environment that those components build, connect, depend and define each other (Saat, 2015: 1).

One main component in education is learners. Learners are society members who seek to develop their potentials through learning process available at certain pathways, levels and types of education (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 on the National Education System Article 1 Paragraph 4). In addition, learners are also defined as educational input that determines the success of educational process (Hasbullah, 2010: 121).

Learners are the main subjects in education who have duty to learn, both in school and outside the school (Djamarah, 2011: 80). Learners are individuals who are not dependent on others or can be referred to as self-determining individuals (Imron, 2012: 4).

Learners are a human component occupying as central position in the process of Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM) (Sardiman, 2012: 111). Besides, learners are also considered as a whole society or individual and will be processed through the educational system, so they are able to be a qualified and dignified human beings in accordance with educational objectives (Team of Lecturers of Education Administration, 2014: 204).

Therefore, it can be concluded that learners are society members who are considered as input and the main subject in education seeking to develop self-potential through Teaching and Learning Activities process in order to be able to be a qualified and dignified human being. Therefore, learners have to be well managed.

“Management is a scientific job to identify the best way to carry out certain tasks” (Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2012: 6). Learners management is a process of setting up activities regarding learners matters to achieve educational goals (Hadiyanto, 2013: 5). Activities in learners’ management include learner planning, new learner admission, new learner orientation, regulating the presence and absence of learner, organizing learner grouping, organizing learner evaluation, arranging rate development, arranging mutation and drop out, and regulating the code of ethics, courts as well as student discipline (Imron, 2012: 5).

Learners management begins with learner planning and new learner admission activities. New Learner Admission Activities abbreviated as PPDB are the acceptance of new learners in kindergarten and school (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2019). PPDB is a process of registration and service of new learners at school level with the requirements set by the school (Mustari, 2014: 111). PPDB is an administrative process carried out annually to select prospective learners, whether junior high school, senior high school or vocational high school based on certain standards in order to continue to the higher-level education (Nizarman, 2015: 225). Therefore, it can be concluded that PPDB is the administrative process including registration activities and services of new learners at a school level through certain requirements and implemented annually. PPDB is conducted to select prospective learners, whether junior high school, senior high school, or vocational high school based on established standards.

Currently, PPDB activities are carried out through zoning system. Zoning is a PPDB system emphasizing the distance or radius between a students’ residence and the school. Therefore, students who are closer to the school, the more chance to have educational services from that school (Nurlailiyah, 2019: 14).

Zoning is defined as a division of an area into several parts in accordance with the functions and objectives of management that become the main foundation in the school reform designing ranging from kindergarten to senior high school (Perdana, 2019: 82). The zoning system aims to continue the government efforts to accelerate education equality.

Zoning-based PPDB is an admission activity for new students based on domicile at the nearest zone radius of the school whose determination is adjusted to the regional conditions including the number of capacities from each school with the availability of school-age children in the area (Safarah & Wibowo, 2018: 210).

The zoning policy in PPDB still causes some problems, including the technical implementation of PPDB causing chaos among the society, the availability of public schools is not evenly distributed in all regions, the zoning system with distance priority causes decreasing students motivation because grades or achievements considered undominant, the dichotomy of excellent and non-excellent schools developing in the society and ineffective coordination among institute so the applicable education policy is not sustainable (Wahyuni, 2019: 14).

From the arisen problems, a study of the perception of new learners is needed to be the main object of education towards the implementation of PPDB zoning. Perception is the process of sensing and interpreting thing or a process of acceptance of stimulus by individuals through sensory tools (Walgito, 2010: 1). Perception is also defined as a process of information entry into the human brain that continuously relates to the environment through the five senses (Slameto, 2010: 102). Therefore, the perception of learners can be understood as the process of sensing information received by learners towards a thing.

The problem in this study is how do new learners perceive the implementation of zoning-based PPDB? This study focuses on the perception of new junior high and senior high school students towards the implementation of zoning-based PPDB and the profile of new junior high and senior high school students, including the distance of residence, the entrance and the USBN/UN mark of new learners.

Literature Review

a. Learner Management

Learner management has several objectives, including improving the knowledge, skills and psychomotor, transferring and developing general abilities or intelligence, talents and interests of learner (Badrudin, 2014: 24). In addition, learner management aims to transfer the aspiration, expectation and meet the learner's needs, as well as learner is able to achieve happiness and welfare in a better life and can learn well in achieving goals.

The principles in the management of learners, among which must refer to the prevailing regulations, are seen as an overall part of institutional management (Education Administration Lecturer Team, 2014: 206). In addition, learner management activities must be pursued to unite learner who have diverse backgrounds and differences in order to understand each other and respect each other. Learner management must also uphold the principle that its activities seek to regulate the development of learner' potential, must be able to encourage and trigger the learner' independence and able to run functionally the learner' lives, both in school and in the future.

b. PPDB-Based Zoning

The objectives of the PPDB zoning system are to ensure the new learner admission conducted objectively, transparently, accountable, nondiscrimination and fair in order to encourage increased access to educational services. In addition, to ensure the availability and readiness of educational units, especially, public schools, they are able to provide quality education services (Ministry of Education and Culture, 2018: 14).

Besides, PPDB zoning system aims to ensure equal access and quality of equitable education in each zone or region that is determined through distance learner's residence and ensure the fulfillment of competent educators and education personnel supported by adequate infrastructure and facilities that can be provided and used together

by educational unit in the service or designated zone. PPDB zoning system also aims to control and guarantee the quality of graduates and supervise the process and learning outcomes comparatively and competitively in education services zone in a measurable and sustainable manner.

Purwanti's research results (2018: 5) explained that the implementation of zoning-based PPDB policy in the academic year of 2018/2019 is more effective, when compared to the implementation of zoning-based PPDB policy in the academic year of 2017/2018. That is, although it does not produce significant changes, but it has to be recognized that there are efforts from the government to improve education policies that have been implemented before. Based on the description above, the purpose of this research is to find out the perception of new learners towards the implementation of zoning-based PPDB.

Methods

This research is part of the Education Zoning Implementation Policy Evaluation study conducted in 2019 by the Policy Research Center of the Ministry of Education and Culture. The research method in the study of Evaluation of Education Zoning Implementation Policy was mixed method approach. Mixed method is a research method that combines two research methods at once, namely qualitative and quantitative in a research activity, so the more comprehensive, the more valid, reliable and objective data will be obtained (Sugiyono, 2011: 18).

Primary data related to the motivation of learners is obtained through the dissemination of questionnaires filled out by learners. The data is processed to obtain information about the perception of learners related to the implementation of zoning-based PPDB.

Samples taken in this study used purposive sampling techniques. Purposive sampling technique is a technique of determining samples in an area with a dense category of schools and areas with rare categories of schools. Areas that are classified as dense in the sample are the city of Bandung, Surakarta, and the city of Surabaya. Sample areas are relatively rare schools in Pontianak and Serang. Data analysis techniques using Miles and Huberman models are carried out interactively and continuously, so the obtained data is saturated. The steps in data analysis of this model include data collection, data reduction, data presentation and inference and verification (Miles & Huberman, 2014: 16).

Results and Discussions

New Students of Junior High school and Senior High School Perception of New Students of Junior high and Senior High School.

Based on the perception of new junior high school students who follow the zoning-based PPDB with total of 1,375 respondents, new students at junior high school level agree that the zoning system can provide a sense of justice amounted 74%. This means that the zoning-based PPDB system can provide certainty to children who live close to the school to make them able to enter the intended school regardless of academic achievement.

The students were asked if the zoning system could eliminate favorite school labels, the students who answered agreed is 53% and those who disagreed is 47%. It shows that school with favorite label still remains as a favorite, because it is related to the facilities and infrastructure as well as the implementation of the learning process existing today in the school.

Figure 1: Perception of Junior High School Students in Grade VII (N = 1,375)

The students are asked about the zoning system, students do not need to study hard because the zoning system provides certainty for students close to where they live and resulted amount 90% students who disagree. It means that zoning system does not decrease the spirit of learning. If there is an opinion that students' motivation to learn to go down, this is an individual problem.

The students were asked that the zoning system could save money, 67% of the students agreed and 33% disagreed. This means that the zoning system can save money because students are close to home or shelter.

Based on the perception of new high school students who follow the zoning-based PPDB with a number of respondents 1,525, the result is slightly different from the new students of junior high school level from senior high school. It is stated that the zoning system can provide a sense of justice amounted 45% and who expressed disapproval is 55%. That is, the zoning-based PPDB system for new students of senior high school still does not provide a sense of justice.

The students were asked if the zoning system could eliminate favorite school labels, 72% of students and those who disagreed are 28%. This suggests that with the school zoning system that originally got the favorite label will be lost, because all students can enter without considering academic achievement.

Figure 2: Perception of Senior High School Students Grade X (N = 1,525)

When senior high school students are asked about the zoning system, students do not need to study hard because the zoning system provides certainty for students who are close to where they live to be accepted, then the students who answer disagree are 80%. That is, the zoning system does not decrease the spirit of learning. There is information that there is a child who states the motivation of learning is down, it is an individual problem.

When students were asked that the zoning system could save students money, there are 62% students agreed and 38% disagreed. This means that the zoning system can save money on snacks, because students are close to home.

Profile of New Students of Junior High school and Senior High School

The things discussed in the new students of junior high and high school through three aspects including the distance of residence of new students, the entrance of new learners, USBN / UN scores of new learners.

New Junior High School Students

Based on data and information obtained from the implementation of PPDB junior high school based on zoning in 2019, the condition of the distance between students and the school has shown that most of the students are in a position close to the school. As Shown in Figure 3, that the distance from where the learner lives with the school is mostly less than 2 km. This shows that with PPDB junior high school through zoning-based, it is more guaranteed that students who live close the school to get the intended school.

**Distance of Students' Residences to school zoning-based
academic year 2019/2020**

Figure 3: Distance between Students' Residences and School

Junior high school students based on residences are Surabaya amounted 1,852 students, followed by Surakarta amounted 1,267 students, Pontianak amounted 544 students and Bandung amounted 260 students. The distance of home is classified into five categories, including 0-1 km, 1-2 km, 2-3 km, 3-4 km, 4-5 km and 5 km more. The distance of 0-1 km is located in three cities, including Surabaya (30%), Bandung (66%) and Pontianak (48%). In contrast, the smallest residential distance is Surabaya (2%) and Surakarta (3%) with distance of 4-5 km, Bandung (3%) with a distance of 3-4 km and Pontianak City (3%) with a distance of more than 5 km. Thus, it can be concluded that in these four cities have followed the zoning rules, so these are more at a small distance of 0-1 km and 1-2 km.

Based on the obtained data, junior high school in new students' admission has gone through the zoning system. New junior high school students based on the most admission routes are Surabaya city amounted 2,216 students, followed by Surakarta city amounted 1,194 students, Pontianak City amounted 429 students and Bandung amounted 293 students. The learners' admission process consists of three aspects, namely zoning, achievement and transfer of parental duties. Based on the admission route, the highest route is through zoning in all cities, namely Surabaya (93.7%) Bandung (88.7%), Surakarta (91.5%) and Pontianak (75.1%). Therefore, it can be concluded that the zoning system has been well implemented in the four cities. This is shown in Figure 4.

Admission Entry of New Students of academic year 2019/2020

Figure 4: New Learner Entrance

Based on USBN scores data in junior high school shows the various of academic ability. This is shown in Figure 5, it was illustrating that academic ability in new learners in one class is different from low and high ability.

USBN Scores of Junior High School New Students of Academic Year 2019/2020

Figure 5: Average USBN Scores of Junior High School New Students

The greatest number of junior high school new students from USBN score is Surabaya amounted 2,914 students, followed by Surakarta amounted 1,369 students, Pontianak city amounted 655 students and Bandung amounted 554 students. New learners' USBN scores consist of lowest grades, average grades, and highest grades. The results showed that the highest score in four cities is almost similar between 294 (Surabaya), 278 (Bandung), 298 (Surakarta) and 286 (Pontianak), but when viewed the average scores, it results if Surabaya (241) is the largest, Bandung (217), Surakarta (194) and Pontianak (188). The conclusion is there is no relation between new learners when viewed from USBN results with zoning system determination. Therefore, this zoning system, the new learners have heterogeneous abilities.

New junior high school students gave a perception of zoning-based PPDB amounting to 1,375 students. New students of junior high school agree that the zoning system can provide a sense of justice amounted 74%. It means that the zoning-based PPDB system can provide certainty to students who live close to the school to be able to enter the school regardless of academic achievement.

The students were asked if the zoning system could eliminate favorite school labels or not. It is resulted that 53% agree and 47% disagree. It shows that the school that have the favorite label still remains as favorite one, because it is related to the facilities and infrastructure and the implementation of the learning process.

Figure 6: Perception of Junior High School Students in Grade VII (N = 1,375)

Students were asked regarding zoning system, if students do not need to study hard because it provides certainty for students who are close to school, resulted 90% students disagree. That is, the zoning system does not decrease the spirit of learning. There is issue stating that motivation of students in learning is down, this is an individual problem.

When students were asked that the zoning system could save money, resulted 67% agree and 33% disagree. It means that zoning system can save money on snacks.

New Students of Senior High School

Based on data and information obtained from the implementation of PPDB senior high school zoning-based in 2019, the condition of residential distance with the school has shown that most of the students are in a position close to the school. As shown figure 7, the distance of residence of learners, less than 2 km. It shows that with PPDB senior high school based on zoning system is more guarantee new high school students who live close to the school to get the intended school.

Distance of Students' Residences to school zoning-based academic year 2019/2020

Figure 7: Distance from Senior High School Students' Residence to School

New students of based on the most entrance routes are Surakarta amounted 2,266 students, followed by Pontianak with 1,640 students, Surabaya with 1,136 students and the smallest is Bandung amounted 1,073 students. The entrance of learners consists of three aspects including zoning, achievement and transfer of parental duties. Based on the entrance route, the highest zoning are Bandung (89.9%) Surakarta (80.3%), Pontianak (86.0%) and Surabaya (73.9%). While, there are 25% through achievement entrance route. Therefore, it can be said that the zoning system has been well implemented in the four cities.

Based on the data obtained, all high schools accept new learners through zoning system. It shows that in the sample area of senior high school, most new learners enter the zoning system with proportions in accordance with The Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 20 of 2019.

Figure 8: Entry pathway for Senior High School Students

New students of senior high school based on the most entry pathway is Surakarta amounted 2,266 students, Pontianak amounted 1,640 students, Surabaya amounted 1,136 students and Bandung amounted 1,073 students. The entry pathway of learners consists of three aspects including zoning, achievement and transfer of parental duties. Based on the entry pathway, the highest is Bandung (89.9%), Surakarta (80.3%), Pontianak (86.0%) and the lowest is Surabaya (73.9%). Therefore, it can be concluded that zoning system has been well implemented in the four cities.

Based on UN score data in senior high school shows that academic ability is various. This is shown in Figure 9 which illustrates that the academic abilities of new learners in one class vary from low to high ability.

The UN Average Score of New Students of Senior High School of Academic Year 2019/2020

Figure 9: The UN Average Score of New Students of Senior High School

There is no correlation between new senior high school students viewed from UN scores with the determination of zoning system. Therefore, it can be said that new high school students have heterogeneous abilities.

There are 1525 students of new senior high school students give a perception of zoning-based PPDB. Senior high school students agree that the zoning system can provide a sense of justice as much as 45% and 55% students who disagree. The zoning-based PPDB system for new students of senior high school still does not provide a sense of justice.

The students were asked if the zoning system could eliminate favorite school labels or not, 72% of students agree and 28% disagreed. This suggests that with the school zoning system that has favorite label will be lost, because all students can enter without considering academic achievement.

The students were asked about zoning system where the students do not need to study hard because it provides certainty for close residence students, resulted 80% students disagree. The zoning system does not decrease the spirit of learning. If there is opinion if learning motivation down, it is an individual problem.

The students were asked that the zoning system could save money, 62% students agreed and 38% disagreed. That is, the zoning system can save money on snacks.

Figure 10: Perception of Senior High School Students Grade X (N = 1,525)

Conclusion and Suggestion

Conclusion

The results show that the zoning-based PPDB for junior high school and senior high school can provide certainty for children who live close to the school to be able to enter the target school regardless of academic achievement. Schools that initially received favorite label are still favorites, because they are related to the facilities and infrastructure as well as the implementation of the existing learning process at the school. In addition, the zoning system based on student perceptions does not reduce enthusiasm for learning. The zoning system has been well implemented in four cities, including Surabaya, Bandung, Surakarta and Pontianak.

Suggestion

Based on these conclusions, several suggestions can be formulated, including the government needs to evaluate the distribution of schools so that the existence of schools is evenly distributed in an area. Zoning-based PPDB socialization in the school environment needs to be maximized. The principal should improve the quality of facilities and infrastructure for the implementation of the teaching and learning process in schools.

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